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Seismic risk assessment of a crude oil refinery testbed: Alternative fragility approaches

Nikolaos D. Karaferis^{a,*}, Vasileios E. Melissianos^a, Konstantinos Bakalis^a,
Athanasia K. Kazantzi^b, Dimitrios Vamvatsikos^a

^a School of Civil Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Athens, Greece

^b Department of Civil Engineering, International Hellenic University, Serres, Greece

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ABSTRACT

A crude oil refinery is employed as a benchmark to test a fundamental assumption in the seismic risk assessment of asset portfolios, i.e., that a fragility function can characterize an asset (or class thereof) with negligible loss of fidelity. Although this is often taken as granted, it also implies that one should not care about breaking the correlation in response that should exist between similar assets subjected to the same ground motion. After all, this is a direct consequence of the summarization of multiple structural analysis results into a single fragility curve that is only parameterized by the (typically scalar) intensity measure. The alternative is to separately consider individual ground motion records and only aggregate per-record results at the final level of impact metrics. Stacking the deck against the conventional approach, a refinery offers an ideal testbed of interconnected assets and multiple refining processes. The results highlight that wherever multiple similar or identical assets are involved in a system disruption, breaking their record-to-record response correlation can severely bias the assessment results.

1. Introduction

Fragility curves are typically employed to compute the probability of a structure, or a class of similar structures, reaching or exceeding a limit state for a given level of a scalar seismic intensity (e.g., Refs. [1–9], fragility curves based on vector intensity measures are beyond the scope of this study). By nature, they represent a summarized view of structural performance, which becomes more apparent when employing response history analysis. Therein, any fragility stands as an aggregation of the results of multiple analyses under different ground motion records and intensity levels into a single curve that only retains the intensity measure as its sole link to the seismic hazard. This aggregation retains the record-to-record variability of the structural responses but masks the correlation between the response and seismic signal characteristics other than the intensity itself (e.g., spectral shape, frequency content, or the timing of distinct pulses in the waveform of the ground motion record). Going down the fragility aggregation path does not necessarily imply a loss in fidelity, especially when one is concerned with cumulative metrics of impact, such as average annual losses, percentages of buildings in a given damage state etc. Such “grouping” operations tend to diminish the effect of correlation with the record signal characteristics, a property that fits well with the use of class fragilities in portfolio loss assessment (e.g., Refs. [10–17]).

* Corresponding author. School of Civil Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Heroon Polytehneiou 9, Politehneiupoli, 15772, Zografos, Attika, Greece.

E-mail address: nkaraferis@mail.ntua.gr (N.D. Karaferis).

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At the same time, by aggregating one disregards, or more accurately, covers-up some aspects related to the characteristics of a specific seismic event. For instance, the spectral shape of a certain ground motion record could affect significantly the responses of a subset of the investigated structures. This condition becomes more evident when critical facilities and other complex systems are examined, where system-level consequences (e.g., loss of functionality, downtime, cascading effects, etc.) can be highly sensitive to the damage sustained by their individual critical assets. Examples of such systems are (i) nuclear powerplants, whose safety is often based on highly-redundant but often identical units, such as diesel generators, piping, and pumps (e.g., Refs. [18–20]), (ii) transportation/transmission systems, such as a highway or a pipeline where the failure of a single bridge [21–23] or pipeline segment [24–27] can undermine the operability of the entire system, and (iii) industrial infrastructure, e.g., chemical process plants or crude oil refineries [28–32].

Crude oil refineries, in particular, are critical energy infrastructure that can affect the environment and economy at the regional, national, or even multinational scale. Large amounts of flammable, toxic, and explosive materials are circulated, processed, and stored within a refinery. Safeguarding these facilities against earthquake-induced damages and minimizing the potential consequences is of vital importance. Failure consequences may involve injuries and fatalities, environmental pollution, direct monetary losses, as well as extended downtime with associated indirect losses that may extend to influencing oil product prices and the economy at large. Even though the design, operation, and maintenance of refineries are strictly regulated, seismically-triggered Natural-Technological (NaTech) accidents still occur [28,33–37]. The latter highlight, among others, the need to advance our approaches regarding risk assessment and the pertinent decision-making for the design and implementation of proactive actions. Over the years, several studies aiming to mitigate or better define the actual risk of a refinery have been developed, including accident scenario analysis, cascading events, impact analysis, and early warning systems [38–46].

Contrary to typical portfolio assessment studies, crude oil refineries are integrated systems comprising a variety of diverse structures that are operationally heavily interconnected and with very different dominant failure mechanisms. Even a minor failure of a single structure may trigger costly disruptions to the entire facility operations [28,29,33]. In other words, the specific assets that remain operational after an earthquake and those requiring interventions or repairs, could have a very different impact on the post-earthquake functionality of the facility, considering also any potential cascading events. Hence, they become fertile ground for investigating the fidelity of alternative seismic risk assessment methods.

The primary concern is whether and to what extent the classic approach of utilizing aggregated (conventional) fragility curves, *measurably* breaks the chain of causality that would normally appear within a given event. To explore the impact of this issue, individual ground motions are treated as separate events across all refinery assets, to the extent of forming record-specific fragility curves (e.g., Refs. [47–49]) that are considered separately in subsequent calculations, i.e., without undertaking any in-between aggregations across the different seismic records. The proposed alternative approach is tested on an open-source refinery testbed [50] as a case study, employing alternative metrics to evaluate the performance of the refinery and understand the impact magnitude (if any) of our underlying assumptions.

2. Conventional versus per record fragilities

Fragility curves offer the probability of violating (or exceeding) a limit state, LS, of interest parameterized on a (typically scalar) seismic intensity measure, IM. They can be derived in a variety of ways, analytically (e.g. [51]) or through empirical data (e.g. [52, 53]), but herein our focus will be on the analytical variety, numerically assessed via structural models (e.g., Refs. [54–57]). The formal definition of fragility is:

$$F_{LS}(IM) = P[LS \text{ violated} | IM] = P[D > C_{LS} | IM] \quad (1)$$

where $F_{LS}(\bullet)$ is the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of its argument, D is the demand in terms of the engineering demand parameter (EDP) given the IM, and C_{LS} is the EDP capacity threshold paired to the specific limit state. When the EDP capacity threshold is exceeded, there is a limit state violation that signals the structure transitioning into a higher damage state (DS). For the typical lognormality assumption [58], fragility may be expressed as:

$$P[D > C_{LS} | IM] = \Phi\left(\frac{\ln IM - \ln IM_{LS50}}{\beta_{LS}}\right) \quad (2)$$

where IM_{LS50} is the median (50 %) value of the IM required to exceed LS, and β_{LS} is the corresponding lognormal dispersion; in the context of Incremental Dynamic Analysis (IDA, [59,60]) this can also be interpreted as the standard deviation of the natural logarithm of the set of IM values (one per ground motion employed) that results in LS violation. The lognormal parameters are abbreviated as $\mu = IM_{LS50}$ for median and $\sigma = \beta_{LS}$ for the overall dispersion, optimally incorporating both record-to-record variability and any additional uncertainties in the structure or its LS capacity (e.g. see Refs. [61,62]). Alternatively, when nonlinear response history results are available, one may opt to employ fragility curves defined via the empirical CDF of the respective record-by-record results (i.e., without applying any fitting). In the following, this is the default approach employed in all investigations, while the corresponding lognormal fits are only used for illustration purposes of asset fragilities.

Let us now consider a single refinery asset, namely a spherical pressure vessel supported by X-braced steel columns [50,63]. Its structural response is largely determined by the amount of fuel stored, denoted by the fill ratio (FR). For illustration purposes, two FR levels are considered: (i) a two-thirds-full vessel ($FR = 0.65$) and (ii) an almost full one ($FR = 0.95$). The corresponding impulsive masses of the vessels are 906.2Mgr and 2162.52Mgr, respectively, leading to periods of $T = 0.47s$ and $T = 0.65s$. Both fragilities

correspond to a low damage state of the first yielding of any of the tank-supporting braces in tension. To be able to compare the fragility of these two versions of the same structure, we need a common IM. Following [63] this is the average spectral acceleration, $AvgSa(0.1 : 1.0s)$, evaluated over a period range of 0.1s–1.0s with an increment of 0.01s. Reasonably, the full vessel ($FR = 0.95$) is anticipated to be the more vulnerable, with its respective fragility yielding higher probabilities of exceedance for lower IM levels. Employing IDA under a hazard-consistent set of thirty ground motion record pairs (see Ref. [50]) confirms our intuition, as evident in Fig. 1 (see also [63]). For reference, the lognormal parameters of the fragilities are:

- Pressure vessel with $FR = 0.95$: $\mu = 0.37, \sigma = 0.41$
- Pressure vessel with $FR = 0.65$: $\mu = 0.54, \sigma = 0.38$

Interestingly, IDA allows us to perform the same fragility derivation process on a record-by-record basis, yielding exactly one fragility curve per record [47–49], so-called “per-record” fragility, where the only dispersion comes from the structure and its C_{LS} capacity. In this context, a single ground motion record is used to compute the probability of exceeding a specified threshold. Consequently, if no additional sources of variability are incorporated into the analysis, the exceedance probability for a given IM level will be either 0 or 1, strictly determined by the calculated structural response and the corresponding EDP threshold C_{LS} to determine limit-state violation. However, when other sources of uncertainty are introduced, such as the variability in said EDP threshold, the fragility function for each individual record resembles a classic fragility curve—albeit one with reduced dispersion since record-to-record variability is now explicitly accounted for via the population of the record-specific fragilities. It is important to note that the spread of these per-record fragility curves is influenced by the efficiency of the selected IM, which may be more optimal for one structure (or version thereof) than another.

These fragilities are shown in Fig. 1 and, although the ensemble of the thirty per-record curves clearly follows the overall verdict on increased vulnerability of the full tank, this is not necessarily the case if examined on a one-by-one basis. Consider the two record-specific fragilities highlighted in Fig. 1, produced for records R5 (TMB, Parkfield 1966) and R18 (TCU141, Chi-Chi 1999). R5 is clearly more aggressive for the $FR = 0.65$ vessel, while it is relatively benign for the $FR = 0.95$ one; R18 behaves exactly in the opposite manner. Such results are not as peculiar if the spectral content of the records is taken into consideration. The spectra of R5 and R18 are presented in Fig. 2, showcasing the geomean spectral acceleration of the two horizontal components and the respective values at the impulsive fundamental periods of the pressure vessel with $FR = 0.65$ and $FR = 0.95$. To also account for the differing masses, the resulting base shear values (ignoring the influence of the convective mass for simplicity) for R5 are

$$V_b^{R5} FR = 0.65 = 0.504g \times 906.2Mgr = 4.48MN$$

$$V_b^{R5} FR = 0.95 = 0.154g \times 2162.52Mgr = 3.27MN$$

while for R18

$$V_b^{R18} FR = 0.65 = 0.301g \times 906.2Mgr = 2.68MN < V_b^{R5} FR = 0.65$$

$$V_b^{R18} FR = 0.95 = 0.251g \times 2162.52Mgr = 5.32MN > V_b^{R5} FR = 0.95$$

It is no wonder then that record R5 is more aggressive towards $FR = 0.65$, an effect that in terms of the conventional “overall” fragilities approach ends up being “averaged” out of the calculations.

One should expect similar issues to appear when considering any number of different assets subject to the same/similar ground motion within a confined geographic area, such as an industrial facility, since such differences relate to the different structural

Fig. 1. Overall fragility disaggregation to per-record fragilities for a spherical pressure vessel with (a) $FR = 0.65$ and (b) $FR = 0.95$. An example of two record-specific fragilities (records R5 and R18) for both FR cases are shown with dashed red and blue color, respectively.

Fig. 2. Geomean spectra of (a) record R5 and (b) record R18 scaled to $PGA = 0.30g$. The impulsive periods of the pressure vessels are shown with dashed lines, namely $T = 0.47s$ for $FR = 0.65$ and $T = 0.65s$ for $FR = 0.95$.

characteristics of the assets at hand. For example, a specific ground motion could be more aggressive towards certain assets of a given type or given vibrational characteristics, while other ground motions could affect a different group. The difference in FR-dependent vessels is more striking as their content (and associated dynamic characteristics) is also uncertain; thus, the same record may affect to a different degree seemingly-identical storage assets, as e.g. within the group of the four spherical pressure vessels of the case study refinery. Conventionally, one would only employ the overall fragility, aggregating all individual record-level results into a single probabilistic distribution. As happens with every aggregation, one gains in simplicity, but loses in correlation. In this case, it is the waveform correlation that is lost as, by definition, only information relayed by the IM is maintained in the compact nature of the fragility curve. Other waveform-specific nuances, such as those displayed in Fig. 2, are lost in the process and essentially spread out within a given fragility.

Instead, per-record fragilities can fully preserve the waveform correlation. Although they have already appeared in the risk assessment literature (e.g., Refs. [47–49]) they were only an intermediate product on the way to deriving the overall record-agnostic fragility. By contrast, we shall maintain the “per-record” fragility information all the way down to the evaluation of the system-level performance to enable considering the effect of the individual ground motion characteristics. For the case at hand, the aforementioned procedure results in thirty different seismic assessments of the refinery, each one corresponding to an individual ground motion record pair. By not neglecting the effect of the individual ground motion characteristics under the vast record-to-record variability, it is argued herein that a system-level assessment could render more accurate risk estimates since the correlation between the ground motion characteristics and the corresponding asset damages is maintained throughout the evaluation process. Another advantage of per-record fragilities is their inherently lower dispersion, as they are influenced solely by uncertainty sources other than the record-to-record variability, herein limited to EDP threshold uncertainties (expandable to include, e.g., model type or model parameter uncertainty (e.g., Refs. [62,64]).

Fig. 3. Plan view of the crude oil refinery testbed.

Consequently, when used in system evaluations, they help reduce computational noise for a given event.

Although we will only employ IDA, this does not mean that other methods of analysis cannot take advantage of the same concept. For example, multi-stripe analysis (MSA, [65]), enjoys the exact same benefits as IDA, as a per-record analysis can also be performed. The only notable difference is that different records at different intensity levels may be employed in MSA and therefore the concept of a record-specific fragility is not necessarily applicable. Otherwise, the same concepts apply since on each IM level per-record results can still be employed separately to evaluate the performance of the facility, aggregating the damage results after the performance evaluation or consequence analysis. On the other hand, the same cannot be claimed for cloud analysis [66,67], at least not in its conventional approach of modeling the IM-EDP relationship via a simple power law regression model [68]. In order to comply with the per-record analysis concept, one should introduce an appropriate correlation model across all assets examined to ensure that record-to-record linking is retained within this new surrogate model that will represent individual record results in cloud analysis. This poses a modeling challenge that scales with the number of different assets involved.

3. Refinery model overview

3.1. Exposure model

A virtual crude oil refinery testbed [32,50] is adopted as a case study to test and examine the differences between the alternative seismic risk assessment approaches. The overall layout of the case study facility and the location of the critical assets at risk are depicted in Fig. 3. The refinery assets are categorized into two broad categories (Table 1), namely fuel storage assets and refining process assets. The former includes atmospheric liquid storage tanks (anchored or unanchored) and spherical pressure vessels, while the latter category includes the structures that take part in the processing of crude oil to final products, which are the process towers, the equipment-supporting building-type structures, the horizontal and vertical cylindrical pressure vessels, the main flare, and the chimneys. These structures have been examined in detail previously [9,63,69–71], except for the cylindrical pressure vessels (horizontal and vertical), for which the seismic fragilities were obtained from the PEC report [72]. Otherwise, reduced-order structural models of the assets were developed in the open-source platform OpenSees [73] and were subsequently analyzed via IDA under a hazard-consistent set of ground motion records. All the relevant information about the virtual crude oil refinery testbed is open-access and offered in a dedicated repository [50], including (a) the exposure model, (b) the seismic hazard model and the selected ground motion records, (c) the properties (geometry and materials) of the structures, (d) the definition of damage states for each asset, (e) the IDA results per EDP, (f) the capacity thresholds, and (g) the “overall” fragility curves per damage state.

As mentioned earlier, a critical parameter that governs the seismic response of the fuel storage refinery assets is the fill ratio, FR. It is the ratio of the volume of stored content over the volume of the vessel (see Refs. [32,63,69]). FR crucially affects the performance of the storage assets (i.e., cylindrical liquid storage tanks and spherical pressure vessels) during a seismic event, since it essentially determines their dynamic properties. Depending on the FR of the vessel, the numerical model is assigned an impulsive and a convective mass that affect its modal characteristics and dynamic responses. FR can take values within the range of 0–1, discretized into ten intervals. The median value of each interval is selected to represent it, thus employing discrete fill ratios of $FR = [0.05, 0.15, 0.25, 0.35, 0.45, 0.55, 0.65, 0.75, 0.85, 0.95]$. The seismic performance of the fuel storage refinery assets for each FR value is then represented by a FR-specific fragility set (e.g. as per [63]).

3.2. Refinery operational status

The operational status of a refinery essentially determines the amount of fuel that is circulated, processed, and stored within the refinery; in essence, it determines the amount of flammable material that is present at the site at any time instance. Depending on various internal and/or external parameters, such as maintenance periods and overall fuel demand at different times (seasonality effect), the FR of storage assets varies throughout a yearly period among assets containing the same product and among different storage assets. It has been demonstrated [74] that there are non-negligible variations in the results among different refinery

Table 1

Assets considered in the exposure model of the case study refinery.

Fuel storage assets	Number of assets	Refining process assets	Number of assets
Gasoline tank	6	Process tower	5
Fuel oil tank	2	Flare	1
Marine diesel oil tank	8	30m steel chimney	3
Jet A-1 tank	8	80m steel chimney	1
Naphtha tank	6	RC chimney	1
Crude oil tank	12	1-story RC building (RC1)	3
Diesel tank	4	2-story RC building (RC2)	17
Slop oil tank	2	4-story RC building (RC3)	7
Liquid asphalt tank	4	1-story steel building (ST1)	10
Water tank	2	2-story steel building (ST2)	9
Spherical pressure vessel	4	Horizontal pressure vessel (HPV)	8
		Vertical pressure vessel type CL1 (VPV1)	12
		Vertical pressure vessel type CL2 (VPV2)	8

operational scenarios due to the significant variation of the fuel content in storage assets. Therefore, the following operational scenarios are considered after [74].

- Scenario 1 - “*Typical day of the year*”: The refinery is operating under normal capacity within a typical day of the year. Most tanks and vessels are assumed to have a random FR while $\sim 20\%$ are almost full at $FR = 0.95$ and $\sim 10\%$ are empty for maintenance.
- Scenario 2 - “*Refinery turnaround*”: The refinery is shut down for major periodic maintenance, called turnaround. Most storage assets are full ($FR = 0.95$) or nearly empty ($FR \leq 35\%$), since practically the facility is out-of-order for heavy maintenance.
- Scenario 3 - “*High-winter time and high-summer time*”: Seasonality affects the fuel demand and consequently the operation of the refinery. It is discretized into winter-time and summer-time based on the demand for specific fuel products.
- Scenario 4 - “*Low-demand scenario*”: An extreme scenario, where the refinery production slows down due to a significant and unforeseen reduction of demand that is imposed by external factors, such as very high oil prices or a lockdown. In this case, $\sim 2/3$ of storage assets will be full.
- Scenario 5 - “*Peak-demand scenario*”: The refinery production capacity is increased beyond normal capacity to meet an exceptional high-demand period in the market. The continuous production and sale of products result in $\sim 75\%$ of the tanks having a random FR, while the remaining are empty or full.

In Table 2 a rough representation of the scenarios implemented is presented to provide a more practical context to the interested reader. Specifically, we characterize each storage asset in terms of their FR, as (a) full, for $FR = 0.95$, (b) random, where a random FR is assigned to the asset (c) empty, where the asset is considered with $FR \leq 0.35$. Therefore, for each scenario, out of the total number of assets corresponding to each asset type, the number of assets of each of the above FR categories are reported. For further details on the scenarios defined the interested reader can refer to Melissianos et al., 2024 [74].

3.3. Refinery-level damage states

The failure (either operational or structural) of each asset does not have the same level of impact on the overall operational integrity of the refinery. It is thus necessary to homogenize the asset-level damage states (ds) to a set of refinery-level damage states (DS) that better represent the functionality consequences on the entire facility should a refinery asset be in a particular damage state [32]. To this effect, the homogenization of damage states after [32] is adopted by pairing the asset-specific damage states (ds) to refinery-level (global) damage states (DS).

The classification of the refinery-level DSs provides a structured framework for assessing the impact of seismic events on refinery assets and operations. DS0 represents the baseline condition where no damage is observed, and the refinery operates at full capacity, requiring only routine maintenance. DS1 indicates minor damage, but the facility remains nearly fully operational, with only small-scale repairs required. DS2 causes moderate disruption, where certain parts of the refinery operate at reduced capacity due to damage that demands immediate and significant repair actions. In DS3, damage becomes extensive, and the facility functions only partially, since assets require major repairs to restore operational performance. Finally, DS4 reflects severe damage, where operations are significantly reduced or suspended altogether. In this state, many critical assets require extensive repair or replacement. This progression from DS0 to DS4 allows for a detailed understanding of both the physical damage and the operational implications at each stage regarding the entire facility. It supports effective risk assessment, planning of emergency response, and prioritization of recovery strategies in order to enhance the seismic resilience of refinery systems. The refinery-level DSs are listed in Table 3. In Table 4 the interested reader can examine the asset-level failure modes, associated with each refinery-level DS, providing further insights on what this homogenization process entails.

3.4. Seismic hazard and record selection

Selecting the “most” efficient and sufficient intensity measure (IM) for the analysis of a single asset is essential to reduce the fragility dispersion and offer more reliable seismic response estimates with the use of fewer ground motion records. When it comes to a risk assessment study of an integrated complex system that comprises a variety of assets with very diverse structural and dynamic characteristics, selecting the most efficient and sufficient IM for all structures is a much more challenging task. Usually in such cases, IMs like the asset-agnostic (see Ref. [71]) peak ground acceleration (PGA) or the moderately asset-aware (see Ref. [71]) average spectral acceleration for a range of periods (AvgSa) are adopted in the literature [75–80]. In our investigation, AvgSa is adopted as the IM for the seismic fragility assessment of the refinery assets [32,50], defined as the geometric mean of multiple spectral acceleration values of the two horizontal ground motion components evaluated across a range of periods. The period range is selected to be between 0.1s and 1.0s, with an increment of 0.01s, i.e., $AvgSa(0.1 : 1.0s)$ for it to include the majority of the refinery asset’s periods, thus being an “on average” good performance predictor for the refinery assessment as an integrated system.

The refinery testbed is located in an industrial area west of Athens, Greece [32]. The seismic hazard analysis for the area of interest is performed using the OpenQuake engine [81]. The calculations are based on the results of the 2013 European Seismic Hazard Model [82] resulting to the hazard curve of Fig. 4(a). In Melissianos et al. [50] the interested reader can find all relevant data used for the analysis, alongside the dataset of 30 hazard-consistent ground motion records that are selected by employing the conditional spectrum (CS) approach [83,84] for a 2% probability of exceedance in 50 years. Specifically, a set of 30 “ordinary” (i.e., non-pulse-like, non-long duration) natural ground motion records are selected considering the horizontal components of the excitation in both orthogonal directions. The acceleration spectra of the selected ground motion records are presented in Fig. 4(b) along with the CS targets (i.e., the 2.5%, 50%, and 97.5% percentiles of the target).

Table 2

Fill ratio characterization of each storage asset in terms of the number of assets in each following category depending on the operational scenario examined: full, random FR, and empty.

Storage asset type	Number of assets	Scenarios																	
		1			2			3.1			3.2			4			5		
		full	random	empty	full	random	empty	full	random	empty	full	random	empty	full	random	empty	full	random	empty
Gasoline tank	6	2	3	1	3	2	1	3	2	1	1	5	0	5	1	0	1	4	1
Fuel oil tank	2	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	2	0
Marine diesel oil tank	8	2	5	1	5	1	2	3	4	1	1	7	0	6	1	1	1	6	1
Jet A-1 tank	8	1	6	1	3	2	3	4	3	1	1	7	0	6	1	1	1	6	1
Naphtha tank	6	1	4	1	1	0	5	3	3	0	1	5	0	4	1	1	1	5	0
Crude oil tank	12	3	8	1	6	2	4	5	6	1	3	8	1	9	2	1	2	9	1
Diesel tank	4	1	3	0	2	0	2	1	3	0	1	3	0	3	1	0	1	3	0
Slop oil tank	2	0	2	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	2	0	1	1	0	0	2	0
Liquid asphalt tank	4	1	2	1	2	0	2	2	2	0	1	3	0	3	1	0	1	3	0
Water tank	2	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	2	0
Spherical pressure vessel	4	2	2	0	3	0	1	1	3	0	2	2	0	2	2	0	2	2	0

Table 3
Refinery global Damage States in terms of operational disruption (adapted from Ref. [32]).

Damage States	Level of disruption	Operational status	Repairs required
DS0	None	Refinery is operational at 100 % capacity	No repairs (except routine maintenance)
DS1	Low	Refinery is operational at almost 100 % capacity	Some assets require scheduling of minor repairs
DS2	Moderate	Refinery is operational with some parts at reduced capacity	Some assets require immediate major repairs
DS3	Extensive	Refinery is partially operational at a reduced capacity	Some assets require extensive repairs
DS4	Severe	Refinery is partially operational at low capacity and may be shut down	Many assets require extensive repairs and/or replacement

Table 4
Homogenization of damage states in terms of operational disruption (adapted from Ref. [32]).

Structure	DS0	DS1	DS2	DS3	DS4
	None	Low disruption	Moderate	Extensive	Severe
Unanchored liquid storage tank	—	ds1: Damage to upper shell course	ds2: Damage to upper shell course or base plate failure	—	ds3: Exceedance of elephant’s foot buckling or base plate failure
Anchored liquid storage tank	—	ds1: Damage to upper shell course or anchorage bolt yielding	ds2: Damage to upper shell course or anchorage bolt fracture or base plate failure	—	ds3: Exceedance of elephant’s foot buckling or base plate failure
Buildings	—	ds1: Anchorage failure of at least one component in Importance Category I (IC I)	ds2: Anchorage failure of at least one component in IC II	ds3: Anchorage failure of at least one component in IC III	—
Process tower	—	—	ds1: Damage to connected piping	—	ds2: Local buckling of shell
Steel chimney	—	ds1: Damage to connected piping	ds2: Damage to liner	ds3: Local buckling of shell	—
RC chimney	—	ds1: Damage to connected piping	ds2: Damage to liner or cross-section yielding	ds3: Cross-section failure	—
Flare	—	—	ds1: Damage to equipment	ds2: Damage to vertical piping	ds3: Tensile or buckling structural member failure
Spherical pressure vessel	—	—	ds1: First yielding of any brace in tension	ds2: Yielding of more than 50 % of braces in tension	ds3: Fracture of any brace
Vertical pressure vessel	—	ds1: Minor damage of vessel’s components	ds2: Failure of piping and global collapse of vessel	—	—
Horizontal pressure vessel	—	ds1: Minor damage to piping and structure	ds2: Failure of piping and anchorage	—	—

Fig. 4. Seismic hazard at the refinery’s site: (a) seismic hazard curve and (b) ground motion spectra and CS-targets.

4. Refinery assessment workflow

4.1. Methodology workflow

A total-probability discrete event simulation approach is followed per each IM level (*IML*), essentially discretizing the entire refinery into (i) the $m = 143$ refinery assets, (ii) N realizations of refinery operational status, (iii) one asset DS assignment per refinery realization given the IM. A Monte-Carlo (MC) simulation analysis is performed where N realizations are employed. The N refinery realizations are proportionally paired to operational scenarios according to the annualized frequency of the latter [74]. Within each realization, each storage asset is assigned a single *FR* and its corresponding fragility according to the specifications of the applicable scenario (see Section 3.2). The fragilities employed are either the overall ones, or the per-record fragilities defined. For each realization and *IML*, a specific damage state (DS) is sampled per asset. In the case of overall fragilities, the DS is determined based on the probability distribution derived from the fragility curves, which aggregate the effects of all possible ground motions, providing a record-agnostic estimate of exceedance probabilities. In contrast, the per-record fragility approach introduces an additional level of discretization by performing calculations separately for each individual ground motion record. Specifically, each ground motion is applied to all assets simultaneously, and the algorithm utilizes the corresponding per-record fragility curves to determine exceedance probabilities. Only after these calculations are performed independently for each record, the resulting consequences are aggregated across the entire refinery. This distinction ensures that the per-record approach explicitly accounts for record-to-record variability, while retaining the record-to-damage correlation; instead, the overall approach provides a simpler but less granular assessment.

In more detail, the calculations per realization are carried out as follows:

Step 1. For the fuel storage assets, an *FR* is assigned to the tanks and pressure vessels [Fig. 5(a)], according to the selected operational scenario. Per the scenario specifications, a given percentage of assets receives deterministic *FR* values i.e., $FR = 0.95$ for full tanks, $FR = 0.35$ for nearly-empty tanks, or $FR = 0$ for empty tanks; the remaining ones take a random value within the range of $[0.05 : 0.10 : 0.95]$.

Step 2. For all assets, using their fragility—either overall or per-record for a given record applied to the refinery—the probability of reaching each DS is computed given the IM level. Then, a DS is randomly sampled per the calculated occurrence probabilities for each one of the refinery assets. [Fig. 5(b)].

Step 3. A vector of m DS assignments per asset is assembled for each realization, essentially resulting in a DS “map” of the refinery for each case.

The abovementioned steps are repeated N times, i.e., once per each realization. The resulting DS vectors form an $m \times N$ matrix per *IML*. A schematic illustration of the matrix for a given IM level is shown in Fig. 6. The main difference between using the overall and the per-record fragility approach is that for the latter, the aforementioned process is performed separately per ground motion record. Therefore, the Monte-Carlo analysis is repeated thirty times (equal to the number of records) and consequently yields a separate $m \times N$ array for each record. As a remark, the number of realizations should be high enough to achieve stable statistics for each IM level. Following a sensitivity analysis, and considering that the DS assignment (Step 2) followed a crude MC approach, a suitable number of realizations for the case at hand is equal to $N = 10000$ for the overall fragility case, and $N = 1000$ for the per-record fragility case. It is recalled that the per-record fragilities have lower dispersions and therefore the variability of their results is lower; consequently, a lower number of realizations is required per record, still reaching a somewhat higher total number of 30000 samples versus the 10000 of the overall fragility case. Still, no real optimization was carried out as the entire simulation for all *IML* values rarely lasts more than a few minutes on a typical desktop computer. For the same reason we did not seek some obvious optimizations, such as switching to a stratified sampling in the DS assignment of Step 2. This would easily reduce N by an order of magnitude and reduce the overall running time to tens of seconds.

Fig. 5. Illustrations of Steps 1 and 2: (a) “partial” *FR*-specific fragilities (black lines), selected fragility (red line) according to the *FR* defined within the realization, (b) Assignment of a specific DS to a structure per realization, by random sampling ; two examples are showcased, specifically for $IML_1 = 0.25g$ and $IML_2 = 0.75g$. The white circles represent a random sampling of the damage state for each given IM level.

Fig. 6. Resulting array of the MC analysis, where the number of rows equals the number of refinery assets, m , and the number of columns equals the refinery realizations, N . The array contains the global DS (numbered 0 to 4) per asset and realization. Each array corresponds to a specific IM level for overall fragilities, or a specific IM level and record for per-record ones.

To make such a study computationally feasible, certain simplifying assumptions had to be made. First of all, the limit-state capacities of individual assets are not correlated, even for identical designs of a given asset, e.g., different tanks of the same design, contractor, construction quality, and level of maintenance. Introducing such inter-asset correlations would require some care in sampling EDP thresholds across similar assets (e.g., [63]), or a broader adoption of a damage/response correlation function in the style of [85,86].

Additionally, uniform soil conditions were assumed across the refinery’s relatively compact footprint of approximately 1.8 km × 1.2 km. Given the relatively short distances, spatial variability (e.g., Ref. [87]) in the ground motion intensity and waveform was neglected. As a result, each ground motion record was applied uniformly to all refinery assets. This is essentially an assumption of perfect correlation in waveform and intensity; for accurate application, this should be toned down even at the scale of a kilometer, and it would certainly not hold for facilities with significantly larger footprints. Nevertheless, it is expected that the fundamental advantages and limitations of the two approaches, presented in this study, would remain consistent. These aspects will be further discussed in the following sections.

4.2. Asset-level impact metrics

To highlight the differences between the two fragility approaches, we need to select some indicative metrics to postprocess and characterize their results. The first set comprises, so called, asset-level structural performance check (SPC) metrics and it concerns the structural condition of the assets in terms of global DS reached.

- **SPC1 – Most probable DS per asset:** The most probable DS for a given IM level is assigned to each asset. This is computed by counting horizontally in the results matrix (blue-outlined row in Fig. 6) the occurrences of each DS and selecting the most prolific one. This does not reflect the DS variability in any way, offering a “central” view of the facility that hides extreme results. Still, it is very useful to visualize the “expected” results in the form of maps and identify the typical state of assets in different scenario events.
- **SPC2 – refinery-wide DS percentage:** The second metric is a per realization metric (green-outlined column in Fig. 6). The percentage of all structures being in each (global) DS per realization is computed and then statistics are calculated considering all realizations. The results convey a simple quantification of the overall impact to the refinery, and can be *approximately* tied to further consequences for the entire facility. For example, the percentage of structures in DS4 over all realizations is indicative of long-term shutdown of parts of the refinery.

Both metrics are applicable to both fragility assessment approaches, albeit offering different levels of resolution. The overall fragility case produces a single map (SPC1) or a single set of percentages (SPC2) per IM level, while the per-record one produces thirty (one for each ground motion) that may be aggregated or treated separately, e.g., via a clustering approach to identify typical patterns of disruption after accounting for record correlation [88].

4.3. System-level impact metrics

To properly assess the refinery’s capability to withstand the consequences of a seismic event and to preliminary quantify the potential downtime and operational disruption, alternative business continuity checks (BCC) are introduced. They are based on expert opinion and their occurrence is estimated via performance verifications per realization. They are evaluated similarly to metric SPC2, in the sense of operating along columns in the realization array(s) of Fig. 6. At the same time, BCCs differ as they do not indiscriminately aggregate asset damage, but instead focus on assets related to specific refinery processes, also adding a threshold of acceptability before triggering critical business continuity conditions. This is the ultimate level of our analysis, therefore aggregation can now be

employed without introducing adverse consequences. Thus, “refinery-level fragilities” are computed, either directly for the overall fragility approach, or by aggregating the per-record fragility results. After all, in the end one expects to integrate with typical hazard curves, which is much simpler with aggregated, record-agnostic, results. With this in mind, the BCCs are defined as follows.

- BCC1 – “*Severe safety threat*”: Any of the 4 pressure vessels reaching DS4. The structural failure of a pressure vessel can result in fire and potential explosion. This is considered as a worst-case scenario regarding the safety of a refinery given the extremely flammable and explosive material stored in spherical pressure vessels, typically butane and propane. For example, after the 2011 Tohoku earthquake, Japan, a spherical pressure vessel collapsed and the resulting fire destroyed 17 tanks in the LPG farm [89].
- BCC2 – “*Significant disruption of refining process*”: Any of the 5 process towers attaining DS4. The refining process is significantly affected because there is no redundancy in process towers, where the core chemical and physical procedures of the refining process take place. For example, if the fluid catalytic cracking tower, where hydrocarbon fractions of crude oil are converted into gasoline, alkene gases, and other petroleum products [90], is damaged, then the entire refining process is essentially stopped.
- BCC3 – “*Disruption of gaseous waste release*”: Any chimney (1 RC, 3 Steel 30m, 1 Steel 80m) attaining DS3 (maximum DS for those assets). The refining process is significantly affected because the gaseous wastes cannot be released and consequently numerous refining processes have to be paused. Moreover, due to the limited space within the facility, even the partial collapse of a chimney may damage nearby assets (e.g., Ref. [91]).
- BCC4 – “*Potential disruption of refining process*”: At least ~10 % of RC buildings (i.e., 3 out of 27) and at least ~10 % of Steel buildings (2 out of 19) reaching DS3 (maximum DS for those assets). The operational capacity of the refinery is reduced until damaged equipment is repaired. Typically, there is some redundancy of equipment nested in a building (e.g., there are typically two heat exchangers), but they tend to be identical and thus heavily correlated. Given that some repairs are required for ~10 % of all buildings, disruption cannot be ruled out.
- BCC5 – “*Severe disruption of crude oil supply*”: At least 25 % (3 out of 12) of the crude oil (i.e., refinery input) tanks reaching DS4. The operational capacity of the refinery will be reduced until the damaged tanks are repaired.
- BCC6 – “*Significant disruption of final product storage*”: At least 25 % (8 out of 32) output tanks (i.e. gasoline, fuel oil, marine oil, jet A1, diesel, liquid asphalt) reaching DS4. The operational capacity of the refinery will be temporarily reduced until the fuel content of damaged tanks is transferred to the undamaged ones and needed repairs take place. Moreover, delivery of final products to customers is affected.
- BCC7 – “*Considerable disruption of liquid fuel storage*”: At least ~10 % (5 out of 54) of the total input/output/in-between/water tanks in the refinery reach DS4. The operational capacity of the refinery will be temporarily reduced until the fuel content of damaged tanks is transferred to the undamaged ones and needed repairs take place.
- BCC8 – “*Significant disruption of liquid fuel storage*”: At least ~20 % (10 out of 54) of the total input/output/in-between/water tanks in the refinery reach DS4. The operational capacity of the refinery will be temporarily reduced until the fuel content of damaged tanks is transferred to the undamaged ones and needed repairs take place.

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Damage distribution using the overall fragility approach

The damage distribution across the refinery in the aftermath of an earthquake using the (conventional) overall fragilities is illustrated by adopting two indicative “scenario” IM levels, namely $AvgSa = 0.4g$ and $0.6g$, corresponding to return periods of ~500 and ~1400yrs. The mapping of DSs on the refinery layout per metric SPC1 (see Section 4.2) is offered in Figs. 7 and 8 for the IM two levels, respectively. The most probable DS of each asset is reported, accounting for the combination of all operational scenarios via the annualized weights (see Section 2.2). These maps can help identify the most frequently damaged structures and their location. It should be noted that the numerous refining-process assets are geographically concentrated in the four refining areas, thus difficult to display in a wide map, but at the same time they are not FR-dependent. Therefore, their SPC1 statistics are essentially identically, even if they do not get identical damage in each realization. Therefore, only a single entry appears in the top right of each figure, showing the most frequent DS.

Overall, it turns out that the most vulnerable assets are crude oil tanks, alongside tanks storing especially volatile fuels, such as gasoline and jet fuel. The higher IM level of Fig. 8 causes many more assets to reach higher DSs; more liquid storage assets are now expected to fail, e.g. naphtha tanks, diesel tanks, and even pressure vessels.

The mean percentage of assets in each DS is illustrated in Fig. 9 per metric SPC2 (see Section 4.2), alongside a range around the median indicating plus/minus two dispersions to convey the considerable variability of the numerous realizations. Finally, to showcase the evolution of damage in the refinery for increasing levels of seismic intensity, Fig. 10 shows the median value of the percentage of assets in each DS. It should be mentioned that not all structures can attain all DSs sequentially. Therefore, in some cases, saturation in terms of DS2 and DS3 is observed.

Fig. 7. Refinery layout considering the most probable DS (metric SPC1) by employing the overall fragility approach for $AvgSa = 0.4g$ (detailed list of assets shown in Table 1).

5.2. Damage distribution using the per-record fragility approach

The same exercise as in Section 5.1 is now repeated using the per-record fragilities. As expected, some ground motions are much more damaging than others in terms of consequences to the entire facility. For $AvgSa = 0.4g$, results for the highly-damaging (high DS4 occurrence) records R20 and R22 are presented in Figs. 11 and 12, respectively, while the corresponding map for the low-damaging (high DS0 occurrence) record R9 is shown in Fig. 13. There is significant difference regarding DS assignment not just between the worst and the most favorable cases, but also between the most aggressive records R20 and R22, or any record in the tails of the distribution for that matter. This is an anticipated outcome in view of the non-negligible ground motion variability. The same observations are valid also in the higher IM level case of $AvgSa = 0.6g$, where records R20 and R22 (Figs. 14 and 15) retain their high-damaging role, and record R9 (Fig. 16) its least damaging one. These event-specific outcomes clearly illustrate the differentiation in terms of the impact that is “averaged out” and lost when using conventional fragilities, leading to a less realistic interpretation of the potential refinery-wide consequences.

Fig. 8. Refinery layout considering the most probable DS (metric SPC1) by employing the overall fragility approach for $AvgSa = 0.6g$.

Fig. 9. Average and variability ($\pm 2\sigma$) of the percentage of assets in each DS (metric SPC2) when employing the overall fragility approach for (a) $AvgSa = 0.4g$ and (b) $AvgSa = 0.6g$.

Fig. 10. Average percentage of assets in each DS (metric SPC2) when employing the overall fragility approach for different $AvgSa$ levels.

Fig. 11. DS of refinery assets for ground motion record R20 by employing metric SPC1 and the per-record fragility approach for $AvgSa = 0.4g$.

Fig. 12. DS of refinery assets for ground motion record R22 by employing metric SPC1 and the per-record fragility approach for $AvgSa = 0.4g$.

Fig. 13. DS of refinery assets for ground motion record R9 by employing metric SPC1 and the per-record fragility approach for $AvgSa = 0.4g$.

The mean and $\pm 2\sigma$ variability band in terms of SPC2, i.e., the percentage of structures in DS0, DS3 and DS4, are presented in Figs. 17 and 18 for each ground motion against the record-agnostic view of the overall approach. Two main observations can be drawn: (i) choosing your record chooses the damage, and (ii) not all damage states were created equal. This is most visible when comparing DS3 (and its counterpart DS0) to DS4. The former has a high record-to-record variability, which completely disappears in the latter. The reason is that the vast majority of DS4-reaching assets are FR-dependent: they are tanks that happened to be full when the earthquake struck. The inherent variability in FR introduces noise in the realizations, largely breaking the effect of waveform correlation preserved by per-record fragilities. On the other hand, DS3-reaching assets mainly belong to the refining process and do not depend on FR. Then, the differences from record to record are sharper rather than smoothed over by other sources of uncertainty.

Fig. 14. DS of refinery assets for ground motion record R20 by employing metric SPC1 and the per-record fragility approach for $AvgSa = 0.6g$.

Fig. 15. DS of refinery assets for ground motion record R22 by employing metric SPC1 and the per-record fragility approach for $AvgSa = 0.6g$.

5.3. Business continuity assessment results

Refinery-level BCC exceedance probability curves were calculated using both the overall and the per-record fragility approaches, presented in Fig. 19. There is a clear distinction between metrics BCC1–4 appearing in Fig. 19(a) to 19(d) and BCC5–8 in Fig. 19(e) to 19(h). In the first group, the overall fragility approach is clearly more conservative, introducing a biased prediction of the exceedance probability as early as the first failure of a relevant asset. Perhaps the worst offender is BCC2 where the observed differences are far from negligible above 0.55g. Instead, minimal differences appear for BCC5–8 between the two approaches.

The cause of this different behavior is in the definition of the BCC metrics. BCC1–3 are triggered when any of several similar assets reaches its ultimate damage state. Neglecting correlation per the overall approach will spread the failures among said assets, thus increasing the chances of any single one failing. For BCC4, only a small subset (~10 %) of assets needs to reach failure, similarly

Fig. 16. DS of refinery assets for ground motion record R9 by employing metric SPC1 and the per-record fragility approach for $AvgSa = 0.6g$.

Fig. 17. Overall versus per-record fragility assessment results comparison for $AvgSa = 0.4g$ by employing metric SPC2 in terms of the average percentages of assets in DS0, DS3 and DS4, alongside their variability bands ($\pm 2\sigma$).

bringing up biases in the overall fragility approach. Equally importantly, though, all assets involved in BCC4 are FR-independent. Instead, when either small or large percentages of storage assets are required to fail for triggering BCC5–8, these are FR-dependent and thus introduce considerable additional uncertainty in the assessment. It is recalled that a limited number of tanks is either full or empty, while most of them have a random FR, a condition that depends on the operational status of the refinery [74]. This random “noise” counteracts the effect of waveform correlation, practically removing the observed bias.

Moving a step further towards the quantification of these differences, the mean annual frequency (MAF) is calculated by convolving the refinery-level fragility curve for each BCC with the seismic hazard curve of the site (Fig. 4). The resulting MAFs are listed in Table 5 for both fragility approaches. The observed differences fully support the conclusions drawn by inspecting the refinery-level fragilities.

Fig. 18. Overall versus per-record fragility assessment results comparison for $AvgSa = 0.6g$ by employing metric SPC2 in terms of the average percentage of assets in DS0, DS3 and DS4, alongside their dispersion ($\pm 2\sigma$).

Table 5

Mean annual frequency (MAF) of BCC1 to BCC8 for both overall and per-record fragility approaches alongside their percentage differences.

Fragility approach	BCC1	BCC2	BCC3	BCC4	BCC5	BCC6	BCC7	BCC8
Overall	2.04E-04	2.18E-04	1.84E-04	8.55E-03	6.59E-03	2.15E-03	9.92E-03	4.95E-03
Per-Record	1.75E-04	1.21E-04	1.64E-04	6.55E-03	6.59E-03	2.22E-03	9.74E-03	5.17E-03
Difference (%)	-14.22 %	-44.50 %	-10.87 %	-23.32 %	0.11 %	3.35 %	-1.88 %	4.42 %

Fig. 19. Refinery-level fragilities using overall and per-record assessment results by employing metric 3 and alternative thresholds of the damaged assets: (a) BCC1: any of the 4 pressure vessels attain DS4, (b) BCC2: any of the 5 process towers attain DS4, (c) BCC3: any chimney attaining DS3, (d) BCC4: at least 10 % buildings attain DS3, (e) BCC5: at least 25 % crude oil tanks attain DS4, (f) BCC6: at least 25 % output tanks attain DS4, (g) BCC7: at least 10 % of all tanks attain DS4, and (h) BCC8: at least 20 % of all tanks attain DS4.

6. Conclusions

Alternative approaches for undertaking seismic fragility assessment have been examined to investigate their effect on seismic risk estimates. The focus is on critical interconnected systems comprising numerous assets, some nearly identical, others with divergent geometric and dynamic characteristics. Potential correlations between assets of similar design, construction quality, and/or maintenance have been disregarded, while an assumption of uniform ground motion has been adopted, neglecting any spatial variability of soil conditions and ground motion, which become highly important for facilities of larger footprint. This allowed us to consider each asset on its own and apply the same ground motion across all assets to simulate a single event. Accordingly, two different assessment approaches were investigated, namely the conventional “overall” fragility assessment approach and the “per-record” approach, in which the fragilities are computed separately for each ground motion record. The overall fragility approach essentially averages the expected consequences of individual ground motions, breaking the near-perfect waveform correlation that is expected within a single-event in a geographically constrained area.

Whether this simplification influences the assessment results apparently depends on the characteristics of the assets and system studied, the connectivity/criticality of assets within the system, and the failure modes and associated metrics of interest. In general, for systems comprising multiple nearly-identical assets where the failure of few is enough to trigger critical disruptions, the conventional approach can be highly biased. Where the failure of assets under a given ground motion also depends on other highly uncertain parameters, such as their structural or operational state, contents, etc., then correlated failures under a single recording become rarer, breaking the effect of waveform correlation.

For the crude oil refinery studied, due to the high number of similar structures, both effects are present and either may become dominant depending on (i) which of the multiple refining processes is of interest, (ii) which type of assets it involves, (iii) what metric is employed to quantify the performance. Identifying which combination will lead to results of low fidelity cannot be easily done a priori. In any case, the per-record fragility approach provides more transparency on the potential post-seismic event state of the facility, allowing for the inherent damage-to-record signature correlation to be accounted for in the analyses. At the same time, it allows a more direct interpretation of the consequences associated with a seismic event. This contributes to enhancing decision-making capabilities related to the planning and adoption of the most efficient reactive and proactive strategies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nikolaos D. Karaferris: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Vasileios E. Melissianos:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Konstantinos Bakalis:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Athanasia K. Kazantzi:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Dimitrios Vamvatsikos:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Source data is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11419659>. Data generated in this study will be made available upon reasonable request.

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